

COMPUTATIONAL MODEL FOR DOUBLY CURVED LAMINATED SHELLS BASED ON A REFINED ASYMPTOTIC THEORY

Chih-Ping Wu¹, Jiann-Quo Tarn² and Yang Kai-Lin³

^{1,2,3}*Department of Civil Engineering, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan,
Taiwan 70101, Republic of China.*

SUMMARY: A multilevel computational model based on a refined asymptotic theory is presented. The formulation begins with a Hellinger–Reissner (H–R) functional where the displacements and transverse stresses are taken as the functions subject to variation. Upon introducing a set of appropriate dimensionless scaling and bringing the transverse shear deformations to the stage at the leading-order level, the weak formulation is asymptotically expanded as a series of weak-form equations for various orders. In the multilevel computational model, the transverse stresses and displacements can be interpolated independently. Through successive integration, the transverse stress degrees-of-freedom (DOF) are condensed in the element level. As a result, three midsurface displacement DOF and two rotation DOF for each node in an element are taken as the independent unknowns in the system equations for various orders. The element stiffness matrix for each order level remains unchanged and the forcing vector can be computed from the lower-order solutions. Thus, the solution procedure can be repeated level-by-level in a consistent and hierarchic way. Application of this multilevel computational model to a benchmark problem is demonstrated.

KEYWORDS: refined theory, asymptotic theory, Hellinger–Reissner functional, perturbation, elasticity, laminated shells, thick shells, doubly curved shells

INTRODUCTION

In recent paper [1], a refined asymptotic theory of double curved laminated shells by means of perturbation is proposed. It is an extension of the asymptotic theory [2, 3] developed recently for static and dynamic analyses of the laminated shells where the basic equations for various orders are identical to the system equations of the classical laminated shell theory (CST). By means of bringing the effect of transverse shear deformation to the stage at the leading-order level, the refined asymptotic formulation embraces the first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT) as the first-order approximation. The basic equations for each order level are merely the FSDT equations and remain unchanged. Thus, the accurate solutions can be determined hierarchically

by solving the FSDT equations. Applications to benchmark problems show that the convergent speed of the refined theory is rapid.

As illustrated in recent paper [1], we found there are several significant advantages in the refined asymptotic theory. Thus, the present work aims at developing a multilevel computational model based on the refined asymptotic theory for numerical modeling of the doubly curved laminated shell. The formulation begins with the Hellinger–Reissner (H–R) functional where the transverse stresses and displacements are regarded as the functions subject to variation. After an appropriate non-dimensionalization, bringing the shear deformation effect to the stage at the leading-order level, we asymptotically expand the (H–R) functional as a sequence of functionals for various orders. Upon expressing the field variables in an element in terms of the generalized nodal DOF and then imposing the stationary conditions for the (H–R) functional, we obtain a sequence of the weak-form equations for various orders. Through successive integration, the transverse stress DOF are condensed in the element level and three displacement DOF and two rotation DOF are taken as the nodal unknowns in an element. Accordingly, the element stiffness matrices and forcing vectors for various orders are obtained. It is shown that the element stiffness matrices are merely those of the FSDT finite element model and remain unchanged for various orders, and the forcing vectors can be computed from the lower-order approximations. Thus, the computational model provides a solution procedure which can be repeated by solving the system equations of the FSDT finite element model level-by-level. The accurate results can be yielded.

THEORY

Basic Variational Formulation

Consider an anisotropic, heterogeneous doubly curved shell of thickness $2h$ subjected to lateral loads $q(\alpha, \beta)$ on the top surface $\zeta=h$. The orthogonal curvilinear coordinates are denoted by α, β and ζ . R_α and R_β denote the curvature radii to the middle surface, a_α and a_β are the curvilinear dimensions in α and β directions, respectively.

The current computational model is based on the Hellinger–Reissner (H–R) principle. The H–R variational functional for the problem is

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_R = & \int_{-h}^h \int_{\Omega} [\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}(u_i) - B(\sigma_{ij})] d\Omega d\zeta - \int_{\Omega^+} q^+(\alpha, \beta) u_\zeta(\alpha, \beta, h) d\Omega^+ \\ & - \int_{\Omega^-} q^-(\alpha, \beta) u_\zeta(\alpha, \beta, -h) d\Omega^- - \int_{-h}^h \int_{\Gamma_\sigma} \bar{T}_i u_i d\Gamma d\zeta - \int_{-h}^h \int_{\Gamma_u} T_i (u_i - \bar{u}_i) d\Gamma d\zeta, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $B(\sigma_{ij})$ denotes the complementary energy density function such that $\varepsilon_{ij} = \partial B(\sigma_{ij}) / \partial \sigma_{ij}$; $\varepsilon_{ij}(u_i)$ is the displacement expressions of strains; Γ_σ and Γ_u denote the portions of the the edge boundary where tractions \bar{T}_i are prescribed and where displacements \bar{u}_i are prescribed; Ω represents the shell domain on the α – β plane at a certain thickness coordinate ζ ; $q^+(\alpha, \beta)$ and $q^-(\alpha, \beta)$ are the transverse loads applied on the top surface Ω^+ ($\zeta=h$) and the bottom

surface Ω^- ($\zeta = -h$) of the shell; $d\Omega^+$, $d\Omega^-$, $d\Omega$ are the differential area element on the surfaces of Ω^+ , Ω^- , Ω , respectively.

The displacements (u_α , u_β , u_ζ) and the transverse stresses ($\sigma_{\alpha\zeta}$, $\sigma_{\beta\zeta}$, σ_ζ) are taken as the primary variables, and are subject to variation in the formulation. By imposing $\delta\Pi_R = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta\Pi_R = & \int_{-h}^h \int_{\Omega} \left\{ [\sigma_\alpha (\delta u_{\alpha,\alpha} / \gamma_\alpha + \delta u_\zeta / \gamma_\alpha R_\alpha) + \sigma_\beta (\delta u_{\beta,\beta} / \gamma_\beta + \delta u_\zeta / \gamma_\beta R_\beta) + \sigma_\zeta \delta u_{\zeta,\zeta} \right. \\
 & + \sigma_{\alpha\zeta} (\delta u_{\zeta,\alpha} / \gamma_\alpha + \delta u_{\alpha,\zeta} - \delta u_\alpha / \gamma_\alpha R_\alpha) + \sigma_{\beta\zeta} (\delta u_{\zeta,\beta} / \gamma_\beta + \delta u_{\beta,\zeta} - \delta u_\beta / \gamma_\beta R_\beta) \\
 & + \sigma_{\alpha\beta} (\delta u_{\beta,\alpha} / \gamma_\alpha + \delta u_{\alpha,\beta} / \gamma_\beta) + u_{\zeta,\zeta} \delta\sigma_\zeta + (u_{\zeta,\alpha} / \gamma_\alpha + u_{\alpha,\zeta} - u_\alpha / \gamma_\alpha R_\alpha) \delta\sigma_{\alpha\zeta} \\
 & + (u_{\zeta,\beta} / \gamma_\beta + u_{\beta,\zeta} - u_\beta / \gamma_\beta R_\beta) \delta\sigma_{\beta\zeta} + [\tilde{c}_{13} u_{\alpha,\alpha} / \gamma_\alpha + \tilde{c}_{36} u_{\alpha,\beta} / \gamma_\beta + \tilde{c}_{36} u_{\beta,\alpha} / \gamma_\alpha \\
 & + \tilde{c}_{23} u_{\beta,\beta} / \gamma_\beta + \tilde{c}_{13} u_\zeta / \gamma_\alpha R_\alpha + \tilde{c}_{23} u_\zeta / \gamma_\beta R_\beta - \sigma_\zeta / c_{33}] \delta\sigma_\zeta - (s_{55} \sigma_{\alpha\zeta} + s_{45} \sigma_{\beta\zeta}) \delta\sigma_{\alpha\zeta} \\
 & \left. - (s_{45} \sigma_{\alpha\zeta} + s_{44} \sigma_{\beta\zeta}) \delta\sigma_{\beta\zeta} \right\} d\Omega d\zeta - \int_{\Omega^+} q^+ \delta u_\zeta d\Omega^+ - \int_{\Omega^-} q^- \delta u_\zeta d\Omega^- \\
 & - \int_{-h}^h \int_{\Gamma_u} [(u_\alpha - \bar{u}_\alpha) \delta T_\alpha + (u_\beta - \bar{u}_\beta) \delta T_\beta + (u_\zeta - \bar{u}_\zeta) \delta T_\zeta] d\Gamma d\zeta \\
 & - \int_{-h}^h \oint_{\Gamma} (T_\alpha \delta u_\alpha + T_\beta \delta u_\beta + T_\zeta \delta u_\zeta) d\Gamma d\zeta \\
 & = 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Nondimensionalization

As formulated in earlier papers [1-3], the field variables are made dimensionless by introducing the scaling:

$$x = \frac{\alpha}{R\varepsilon}, \quad y = \frac{\beta}{R\varepsilon}, \quad z = \frac{\zeta}{h}; \quad u = \frac{u_\alpha}{R\varepsilon}, \quad v = \frac{u_\beta}{R\varepsilon}, \quad w = \frac{u_\zeta}{R}; \quad R_x = \frac{R_\alpha}{R}, \quad R_y = \frac{R_\beta}{R}; \tag{3a,b,c}$$

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma_\alpha}{Q}, \quad \sigma_y = \frac{\sigma_\beta}{Q}, \quad \tau_{xy} = \frac{\tau_{\alpha\beta}}{Q}; \quad \tau_{xz} = \frac{\tau_{\alpha\zeta}}{Q\varepsilon}, \quad \tau_{yz} = \frac{\tau_{\beta\zeta}}{Q\varepsilon}, \quad \sigma_z = \frac{\sigma_\zeta}{Q\varepsilon^2}. \tag{3d,e}$$

where $\varepsilon^2 = h/R < 1$ is a small perturbation parameter. R denotes a characteristic length of the shell. Q is a reference elastic modulus.

After introducing Eqn 3 and the essential boundary conditions in Eqn 2, then integrating by parts the terms associated with $\delta u_{,\alpha}$ and $\delta w_{,\zeta}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta \Pi_R = QRh^2 & \left[\int_{-1}^1 \int_{\Omega} \left\{ \left[(\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w} + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{L}_3 \sigma_z)^\top \mathbf{D}_1 - \sigma_{z,z}^\top - \varepsilon^2 (\mathbf{L}_4 \sigma_s)^\top - \varepsilon^4 (\mathbf{L}_5 \sigma_s)^\top \right] \delta \mathbf{u} \right. \right. \\
 & + \left[(\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w})^\top \mathbf{D}_2 - \sigma_{z,z} - \varepsilon^2 l_1 \sigma_z - \varepsilon^4 l_2 \sigma_z + \sigma_s^\top \mathbf{D} + \varepsilon^2 \sigma_s^\top \mathbf{L}_6 \right] \delta w + \left[\mathbf{D} \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{u}_{,z} + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{L}_7 \mathbf{u} + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{L}_6 \mathbf{w} \right. \\
 & + \left. \varepsilon^4 \mathbf{L}_8 \mathbf{u} - \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{S} \sigma_s - \varepsilon^4 \mathbf{L}_9 \sigma_s \right]^\top \delta \sigma_s + \left[w_{,z} + \varepsilon^2 l_3 w + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{L}_{10} \mathbf{u} - \varepsilon^4 l_4 \sigma_z \right] \delta \sigma_z \left. \right\} dx dy dz \\
 & - \int_{-1}^1 \int_{\Gamma_0} (\bar{\mathbf{P}}^\top \delta \mathbf{u} + \bar{P}_z \delta w) d\Gamma dz \Big] = 0, \tag{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{u} = \{u \ v\}^\top$, $\sigma_s = \{\tau_{xz} \ \tau_{yz}\}^\top$, $\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{s}_{55} & \tilde{s}_{45} \\ \tilde{s}_{45} & \tilde{s}_{44} \end{bmatrix}$; $l_i, \mathbf{D}_i, \mathbf{L}_i$ are the relevant matrices.

The Refined Asymptotic Approach

The relationship between the dimensionless transverse shear stresses and strains is

$$\sigma_s = \varepsilon^{-2} \mathbf{C}_s \boldsymbol{\gamma}_s, \tag{5}$$

where $\mathbf{C}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{c}_{55} & \tilde{c}_{45} \\ \tilde{c}_{45} & \tilde{c}_{44} \end{bmatrix}$, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_s = \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{xz} \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{yz} \end{Bmatrix}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{xz} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\zeta}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{yz} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\beta\zeta}$.

As formulated in the earlier paper [1], we realize that the transverse displacement is not explicitly related to the transverse shear stresses while the in-surface displacements are related to the transverse shear stresses at the ε^2 level. In order to account for the effect of transverse shear deformations at the leading-order level, we introduce the auxiliary variables ψ_x, ψ_y associated with the transverse shear deformations and decompose the transverse shear strains as

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}_s = \boldsymbol{\Psi} + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{S} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_s, \tag{6}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Psi} = \{\psi_x \ \psi_y\}^\top$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_s = \{\hat{\sigma}_{xz} \ \hat{\sigma}_{yz}\}$; ψ_x and ψ_y are the average shear rotations at the middle surface, $\hat{\sigma}_{xz}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{yz}$ thus represent the difference between the actual transverse shear stresses and the approximate ones.

Substituting Eqn 6 into Eqn 5, and multiplying both sides of the resulting equation by $\varepsilon^2 \mathbf{S}$, we have

$$\varepsilon^2 \mathbf{S} \sigma_s = \boldsymbol{\Psi} + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{S} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_s. \tag{7}$$

Asymptotic Expansion

We expand the field variables in powers of ε^2 as given by

$$f(x, y, z; \varepsilon) = f_{(0)}(x, y, z) + \varepsilon^2 f_{(1)}(x, y, z) + \varepsilon^4 f_{(2)}(x, y, z) + \dots \tag{8}$$

After substituting Eqns 6–7 into the Eqn 4, and collecting the equal-power term of ε , we obtain

$$\delta\Pi_R = QRh^2(\delta\Pi_{(0)} + \varepsilon^2 \delta\Pi_{(1)} + \varepsilon^4 \delta\Pi_{(2)} + \dots) = 0. \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\Pi_{(0)} = & \int_{-1}^1 \int_{\Omega} \left\{ (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}_{(0)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(0)})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \delta \mathbf{u}_0) - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0),z}^T \delta \mathbf{u}_0 + (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}_{(0)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(0)})^T (\mathbf{D}_2 \delta \mathbf{w}_0) \right. \\ & - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0),z}^T \delta \mathbf{w}_0 + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^T (\mathbf{D} \delta \mathbf{w}_0) + z (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}_{(0)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(0)})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0) + (\mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\psi}_0)^T \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0 \\ & \left. + [\mathbf{u}_{(0),z}^T + (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{w}_{(0)})^T - \boldsymbol{\psi}_0^T] \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)} + \mathbf{w}_{(0),z} \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)} \right\} dx dy dz \\ & - \int_{-1}^1 \int_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{P}^T \delta \mathbf{u}_0 + P_z \delta \mathbf{w}_0) d\Gamma dz - \int_{-1}^1 \int_{\Gamma} z \mathbf{P}^T \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0 d\Gamma dz. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\Pi_{(k)} = & \int_{-1}^1 \int_{\Omega} \left\{ (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}_{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(k)})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \delta \mathbf{u}_k) + (\mathbf{L}_3 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k-1)})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \delta \mathbf{u}_k) - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k),z}^T \delta \mathbf{u}_k - (\mathbf{L}_4 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k-1)})^T \delta \mathbf{u}_k \right. \\ & - (\mathbf{L}_5 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k-2)})^T \delta \mathbf{u}_k + (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}_{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(k)})^T (\mathbf{D}_2 \delta \mathbf{w}_k) - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k),z}^T \delta \mathbf{w}_k - (l_1 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k-1)}) \delta \mathbf{w}_k - (l_2 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k-2)}) \delta \mathbf{w}_k \\ & + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)}^T (\mathbf{D} \delta \mathbf{w}_k) + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k-1)}^T (\mathbf{L}_6 \delta \mathbf{w}_k) + z (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}_{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(k)})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_k) + z (\mathbf{L}_3 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k-1)})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_k) \\ & + (\mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\psi}_k)^T \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_k - z (\mathbf{L}_4 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k-1)})^T \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_k - z (\mathbf{L}_5 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k-2)})^T \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_k + [\mathbf{u}_{(k),z}^T + (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{w}_{(k)})^T - \boldsymbol{\psi}_k^T] \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)} \\ & - \mathbf{S} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{s(k-1)} \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)} + (\mathbf{L}_7 \mathbf{u}_{(k-1)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)} + (\mathbf{L}_6 \mathbf{w}_{(k-1)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)} + (\mathbf{L}_8 \mathbf{u}_{(k-2)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)} - (\mathbf{L}_9 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k-2)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(k)} \\ & \left. + \mathbf{w}_{(k),z} \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k)} + (l_3 \mathbf{w}_{(k-1)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k)} + (\mathbf{L}_{10} \mathbf{u}_{(k-1)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k)} - (l_4 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k-2)}) \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(k)} \right\} dx dy dz \quad (k=1, 2, \dots). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The total rotation $\boldsymbol{\phi} = \boldsymbol{\psi} - \mathbf{D} \mathbf{w}$ and $\mathbf{C} = (R/h) \mathbf{S}^{-1}$.

Multilevel Computational Model

Eqn 9 is an expansion of $\delta\Pi_R$ in terms of even powers of ε . Thus, we have decomposed the H-R functional into functionals of various orders; $\delta\Pi_{(0)}=0$ represents the leading-order approximation to the stationary condition $\delta\Pi_R=0$, $\delta\Pi_{(1)}=0$ provides the ε^2 -order modification, $\delta\Pi_{(2)}=0$ the ε^4 -order modification, and so on.

The Leading-Order Level

The x-y plane of the domain is represented by a finite element mesh and variations of the field variables in an element are expressed in terms of the generalized nodal DOF by

$$\mathbf{u}_{(0)}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e(z), \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_{(0)}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{N}_w \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e(z), \quad (13)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{N}_s \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e(z), \quad (14)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{N}_z \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}^e(z), \quad (15)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}_0(x, y) = \mathbf{N} \boldsymbol{\psi}_0^e, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{N} , \mathbf{N}_w , \mathbf{N}_s , \mathbf{N}_z denote the interpolation functions of x and y , the generalized nodal DOF $\mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e$, $\mathbf{w}_{(0)}^T$, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}^e$ are functions of z , the shear rotation DOF of the midsurface $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_0^e$ are independent of z . As will be shown, the through-thickness variations of the generalized nodal DOF can be derived analytically by successive integration, and the transverse stress DOF are condensed along the way; only the displacement and rotation DOF enter the system equation at each level.

Substituting Eqns 12–16 into $\delta\mathbf{\Pi}_{(0)}$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\mathbf{\Pi}_{(0)} = & \int_{-1}^1 \left\{ \left[\left(\mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1 + \left(\mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2 - \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1 - \mathbf{P}^T \right] \delta \mathbf{u}_0^e + \left[\left(\mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_3 + \left(\mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_4 \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0),z}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_3 + \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 - \mathbf{P}_w^T \right] \delta \mathbf{w}_0^e + \left[z \left(\mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1 + z \left(\mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2 + \left(\boldsymbol{\Psi}_0^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - z \mathbf{P}^T \right] \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e + \left[\left(\mathbf{u}_{(0),z}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1 + \left(\mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 - \left(\boldsymbol{\Psi}_0^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^T \right] \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e + \left[\left(\mathbf{w}_{(0),z}^e \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Phi}_3 \right] \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}^e \right\}, \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1 &= \int_{\Omega_e} (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{N})^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \mathbf{N}) dx dy, & \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2 &= \int_{\Omega_e} (\mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{N}_w)^T (\mathbf{D}_1 \mathbf{N}) dx dy, \\ \boldsymbol{\Psi}_3 &= \int_{\Omega_e} (\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{N})^T (\mathbf{D}_2 \mathbf{N}_w) dx dy, & \boldsymbol{\Psi}_4 &= \int_{\Omega_e} (\mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{N}_w)^T (\mathbf{D}_2 \mathbf{N}_w) dx dy, \\ \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c &= \int_{\Omega_e} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{N} dx dy, & \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1 &= \int_{\Omega_e} \mathbf{N}_s^T \mathbf{N} dx dy, & \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 &= \int_{\Omega_e} \mathbf{N}_s^T (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{N}_w) dx dy, \\ \boldsymbol{\Phi}_3 &= \int_{\Omega_e} \mathbf{N}_z^T \mathbf{N}_w dx dy, & \mathbf{P} &= \int_{\Gamma_e} \mathbf{N}^T \bar{\mathbf{P}} d\Gamma, & \mathbf{P}_w &= \int_{\Gamma_e} \mathbf{N}_w^T \bar{\mathbf{P}}_w d\Gamma, \end{aligned}$$

Ω_e denotes the element domain, \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{P}_w appear only when the element boundaries coincide with the edge boundary on which tractions are prescribed.

At the element level, the condition $\delta\mathbf{\Pi}_{(0)} = 0$ leads to

$$\delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}^e: \quad \frac{d}{dz} \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e = \mathbf{0}, \quad (18)$$

$$\delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e: \quad \frac{d}{dz} \mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e - \boldsymbol{\Psi}_0^e = \mathbf{0}, \quad (19)$$

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e: \quad \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T \mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e - \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^T \frac{d}{dz} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e - \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (20)$$

$$\delta \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e: \quad \boldsymbol{\Psi}_3^T \mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_4^T \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e - \boldsymbol{\Phi}_3^T \frac{d}{dz} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}^e - \mathbf{P}_w = \mathbf{0}, \quad (21)$$

$$\delta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e: \quad \int_{-1}^1 \left(z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T \mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e + z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T \mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_0^e \right) dz - \int_{-1}^1 z \mathbf{P} dz = \mathbf{0}. \quad (22)$$

Successive integration of Eqns 18–22 with respect to z yields

$$\mathbf{w}_{(0)}^e = \mathbf{w}_0^e, \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{(0)}^e(z) = \mathbf{u}_0^e + z \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e, \quad (24)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{s(0)}^e(z) = (\boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^T)^{-1} \int_{-1}^z \left[\boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T (\mathbf{u}_0^e + \eta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e) + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T \mathbf{w}_0^e - \mathbf{P} \right] d\eta, \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{z(0)}^e(z) = & (\boldsymbol{\Phi}_3^T)^{-1} \left\{ \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2^T (\boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^T)^{-1} \int_{-1}^z (z-\eta) \left[\boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T (\mathbf{u}_0^e + \eta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e) + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T \mathbf{w}_0^e - \mathbf{P} \right] d\eta \right. \\ & \left. + \int_{-1}^z \left[\boldsymbol{\Psi}_3^T (\mathbf{u}_0^e + \eta \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e) + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_4^T \mathbf{w}_0^e \right] d\eta - \int_{-1}^z \mathbf{P}_w d\eta \right\} - \tilde{q}^-, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \left[z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T (\mathbf{u}_0^e + z \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e) + z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T \mathbf{w}_0^e + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c^T (\boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 \mathbf{w}_0^e) \right] dz - \int_{-1}^1 z \mathbf{P} dz = 0, \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{w}_0^e , \mathbf{u}_0^e represent the leading-order approximation to the midsurface displacement DOF; $\boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e = \boldsymbol{\Psi}_0^e - \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 \mathbf{w}_0^e$ which represents the total rotation DOF.

After imposition of the lateral boundary conditions on top surface ($z=1$) in Eqns 25–26, then a simplification of the resulting equations, it leads to

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{uu} & \mathbf{K}_{uw} & \mathbf{K}_{u\phi} \\ \mathbf{K}_{wu} & \mathbf{K}_{ww} & \mathbf{K}_{w\phi} \\ \mathbf{K}_{\phi u} & \mathbf{K}_{\phi w} & \mathbf{K}_{\phi\phi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_0^e \\ \mathbf{w}_0^e \\ \boldsymbol{\phi}_0^e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_{u0} \\ \mathbf{F}_{w0} \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi 0} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (28)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{uu} = \int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T dz$, $\mathbf{K}_{uw} = \int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T dz$, $\mathbf{K}_{u\phi} = \int_{-1}^1 z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T dz$, $\mathbf{K}_{wu} = \int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_3^T dz$,

$$\mathbf{K}_{ww} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2^T (\boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^T)^{-1} \left(\int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c^T dz \right) \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2 + \int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_4^T dz, \quad \mathbf{K}_{w\phi} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2^T (\boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^T)^{-1} \int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c^T dz + \int_{-1}^1 z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_3^T dz,$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\phi u} = \int_{-1}^1 z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T dz, \quad \mathbf{K}_{\phi w} = \int_{-1}^1 z \boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T dz + \left(\int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c^T dz \right) \boldsymbol{\Phi}_1^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2, \quad \mathbf{K}_{\phi\phi} = \int_{-1}^1 z^2 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T dz + \int_{-1}^1 \boldsymbol{\Psi}_c^T dz,$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{u0} = \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{P} dz, \quad \mathbf{F}_{w0} = \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{P}_w dz + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_3^T (\tilde{q}^+ + \tilde{q}^-), \quad \mathbf{F}_{\phi 0} = \int_{-1}^1 z \mathbf{P} dz.$$

After carrying out the integral expressions of $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_1$, $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_2$, $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_3$, we have $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_2^T = \boldsymbol{\Psi}_3$, $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_1^T = \boldsymbol{\Psi}_1$. Thus, the coefficient matrix in Eqn 28 is symmetric and $\mathbf{K}_{wu} = \mathbf{K}_{uw}^T$, $\mathbf{K}_{u\phi} = \mathbf{K}_{\phi u}^T$, $\mathbf{K}_{w\phi} = \mathbf{K}_{\phi w}^T$.

Eqn 28 consists of $5n$ equations in $5n$ unknown DOF for an element with n nodes. The resultant shear and moment in the generalized force vector appear only at the boundary nodes on Γ_σ . After assembling the element matrices into system equations and imposing the prescribed essential at the boundary nodes on Γ_u , we can determine the unknown DOF at the interior nodes and at the boundary nodes on Γ_σ , whereas the generalized force components at the boundary nodes on Γ_σ can also be determined. Afterwards, the leading-order approximation to the displacements and stresses are determined by using Eqns 23–26.

Higher-Order Corrections

After the similar manipulation as done at the ε^0 -order level, the ε^{2k} -order corrections to the midsurface displacements ($\mathbf{w}_k^e, \mathbf{u}_k^e$) and rotations (ϕ_k^e) can be determined from

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{uu} & \mathbf{K}_{uw} & \mathbf{K}_{u\phi} \\ \mathbf{K}_{wu} & \mathbf{K}_{ww} & \mathbf{K}_{w\phi} \\ \mathbf{K}_{\phi u} & \mathbf{K}_{\phi w} & \mathbf{K}_{\phi\phi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_k^e \\ \mathbf{w}_k^e \\ \phi_k^e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_{uk} \\ \mathbf{F}_{wk} \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi k} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (29)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{uk} = -\Phi_1^T \mathbf{I}_k(z=1)$, $\mathbf{F}_{wk} = \Phi_2^T \mathbf{I}_k(z=1) - \Phi_3^T \mathbf{J}_k(z=1) - \Phi_2^T \mathbf{K}_k(z=1)$, $\mathbf{F}_{\phi k} = -\Phi_1^T \mathbf{K}_k(z=1)$. For brevity, the detailed expressions of $\mathbf{I}_k, \mathbf{J}_k$ and \mathbf{K}_k are omitted.

It is noted that the coefficient matrix at the higher-order levels is the same as that at the leading-order level, and their nonhomogeneous terms can be computed from the lower-order solutions. Thus, the current computational model provides a solution procedure to yield the three-dimensional solution and this procedure can be repeated in a consistent and hierarchic way.

ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

A $[0/90/0]$ cross-ply laminated spherical shell with shear-diaphragm supports, subjected to $q(\alpha, \beta) = q_0 \sin\pi\alpha/a_\alpha \sin\pi\beta/a_\beta$ is considered. The geometry parameters and material properties used in the computation are $a_\alpha/a_\beta = 1$; $R_\alpha/R_\beta = 1$; $R_\alpha/a_\alpha = 1$; $2h/a_\alpha = 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.09, 0.1$; and $E_l/E_T = 25$; $G_{lT}/E_T = 0.5$; $G_{TT}/E_T = 0.2$; $E_T = 689 \times 10^6 \text{ KN/m}^2$ (10^6 psi); $\nu_{lT} = \nu_{TT} = 0.25$.

Table 1 shows the $\varepsilon^0, \varepsilon^2, \varepsilon^4$ and ε^6 -order solutions of the normalized transverse displacement \bar{w} , $\bar{w} = u_\zeta (2h)^3 E_T 10^3 / q_0 (a_\alpha)^4$, for different ratios of $2h/a_\alpha$. To obtain convergent results, the analysis is carried to ε^2 order in the case of thin shells ($2h/a_\alpha = 0.01$), and to ε^4 order in the case of thick shells ($2h/a_\alpha = 0.1$). Comparisons of the numerical results obtained from a discrete-layer higher-order theory [4], an approximate 3-D elasticity [5], FSDT [6], HSDT [7] and CST [8] are presented. It is found that the ε^0 -order solution of the present asymptotic theory agrees with the FSDT solution. The convergent results are in close agreement with the discrete-layer solution as well as the approximate elasticity solution. Figs. 1-2 consider a $[0/90/0/90/0]_2$ doubly curved shell subjected to a sinusoidal load. The geometry parameters are $a_\alpha/a_\beta = 1$; $R_\alpha/a_\alpha = 1$; $R_\beta/a_\beta = 10$; $2h/a_\alpha = 0.1$. Through-thickness distributions of the transverse shear and normal stresses for the $\varepsilon^0, \varepsilon^2, \varepsilon^4$ orders are presented. As can be seen, the convergent speed of the present asymptotic solution is rapid. The asymptotic solution yields continuous interlaminar stresses through the thickness, and traction boundary conditions at the lateral surfaces are satisfied exactly.

Fig. 1: Distribution of transverse shear stress through thickness of a $[0/90/0/90/0]_2$ doubly curved shell

Fig. 2: Distribution of transverse normal stress through thickness of a $[0/90/0/90/0]_2$ doubly curved shell

Table 1: Center deflection parameter of $[0/90/0]$ spherical shells

$2h/R\alpha$ ($2h/a_\alpha$)	Present study		Wu and Liu [4] (discrete-layer theory)	Fan and Zhang [5] (approximate elasticity solution)	Reddy [6] (FSDT)		Reddy and Liu [7] (HSDT)	Leissa and Qatu [8] (CST)
					($k_1=07$, $k_2=06$)	($k_1=5/6$, $k_2=5/6$)		
0.01	e^0	0.0535	0.0541	0.0541	0.0536	0.0536	0.0535	0.0535
	e^2	0.0541						
	e^4	0.0541						
	e^6	0.0541						
0.03	e^0	0.4397	0.4624	0.4624	0.4487	0.4480	0.4419	0.4379
	e^2	0.4626						
	e^4	0.4624						
	e^6	0.4624						
0.05	e^0	1.0571	1.1723	1.1724	1.1144	1.1052	1.0730	1.0304
	e^2	1.1726						
	e^4	1.1726						
	e^6	1.1723						
0.07	e^0	1.7686	2.0860	2.0863	1.9435	1.9024	1.8231	1.6427
	e^2	2.0848						
	e^4	2.0870						
	e^6	2.0860						
0.09	e^0	2.5224	3.1659	3.1667	2.8953	2.7870	2.6473	2.1746
	e^2	3.1612						
	e^4	3.1674						
	e^6	3.1659						
0.10	e^0	2.9135	3.7664	3.7676	3.4152	3.2588	3.0856	2.4007
	e^2	3.7595						
	e^4	3.7674						
	e^6	3.7664						

CONCLUSIONS

A multilevel computational model based on a refined asymptotic theory is presented for the bending analysis of doubly curved laminated shells. The formulation begins with a H-R functional. By introducing a set of appropriate scaling, asymptotically expanding the field variables in terms of a small perturbation parameter and applying the stationary condition of the H-R functional, we obtain recursive sets of system equations leading to the FSDT equations for various orders. The accurate solution can be obtained by solving the FSDT-type equations level-by-level.

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